

BURDENS AND MANAGEMENT STRIDES OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

This research reviewed the burdens and management strides of COVID-19 pandemic. A meta-analysis method is undertaken in the retrospective study design using basically secondary data. Several relevant articles were randomly selected from highly-rated research database platforms. Only those which met the inclusion criteria were considered for this systematic review. Articles with similar findings were grouped together for analysis. Findings revealed that the enormous effects of COVID-19 burden on management strides were overwhelmed healthcare institutions and systems during peak infection, global economic recession, social disruption, increase in crime rate or insecurity and increase in domestic violence, disorganized educational system, worsened hunger state and agriculture, disruption of culture and religious activities, political disarray, increased xenophobia and racism, and many prolonged health complications. The study also identified fast manufacture of vaccines, narrowing to specific treatment drugs with appropriate dieting. It was recommended that individuals should be encouraged to find healthy supportive ways to cope with stress, such as meditation, journaling, and speaking with a counselor, and practice of good sleep hygiene. There is need to track trends in stress levels and their drivers along with building resilient organization in order to help health care organizations monitor the impact COVID-19 has on their workforce during this pandemic with workload redistribution. Lastly, more vigorous single-dose vaccination against the pandemic with monetary incentive was also considered as a possible option for increased vaccination acceptance in developing countries.